

Contrast the Hemodynamic Parameters, Including Blood Pressure Heart Rate and SpO₂ throughout Spinal Anaesthesia

Jyoti Priya¹, Himanshu Shekhar², Mani Lal Gupta³

¹Senior Resident, Department of Anaesthesiology, BMIMS, Pawapuri, Nalanda

²Senior Resident, Department of Anaesthesiology, BMIMS, Pawapuri, Nalanda

³Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Anaesthesiology, BMIMS, Pawapuri, Nalanda

Received: 10-03-2024 / Revised: 07-04-2024 / Accepted: 05-05-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Himanshu Shekhar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: The study was undertaken in the Department of Anaesthesiology, BMIMS, Pawapuri, Nalanda. The study included 90 patients (Age 20-35 years) undergoing elective caesarean section under spinal Anaesthesia. It provides satisfactory anaesthesia for lower abdominal, urological and lower limb surgeries and it is often associated with a marked fall in blood pressure during and after anaesthesia due to various factors like diminished cardiac output consequent upon decreased venous return due to blockade of sympathetic nerves arising from T₁-L₂ leading to dilatation of both resistance and capacitance vessels and lack of propulsive movement on veins.

Conclusion: Vital parameters were monitored and blood pressure & heart rate reading were taken 3 times at 2 minutes interval and lowest MAP and heart rate were taken as baseline for each group respectively. All the patients were preloaded with 500 ml of ringer lactate solution. Test drug was injected IM just after the induction of spinal anaesthesia. All the patients were observed and hemodynamic data recorded for 60 minutes after spinal anaesthesia. The patients were monitored for hypotension (decrease in MAP > 25% of baseline MAP), bradycardia (heart rate < 50 beats/minute), nausea, vomiting.

Keywords: Hemodynamic, SpO₂, Heart & Spinal Anaesthesia.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Spinal anaesthesia was initially given inadvertently by Corning in 1885 and first planned anaesthesia for surgery in man was performed by August Bier on 16th August 1898. [1]

It provides satisfactory anaesthesia for lower abdominal, urological and lower limb surgeries and it is often associated with a marked fall in blood pressure during and after anaesthesia due to various factors like diminished cardiac output consequent upon decreased venous return due to blockade of sympathetic nerves arising from T₁-L₂ leading to dilatation of both resistance and capacitance vessels and lack of propulsive movement on veins. Secondly paralysis of sympathetic nerve supply of heart and adrenal gland leads to subsequent catecholamine depletion and thirdly ischemia and hypoxia of vital centers leading to depression of circulatory system. It is desirable to record the blood pressure every 5-10 minutes but there is considerable difference of opinion as to the extent to which it should be allowed to fall before corrective measure are to be taken. [2]

Continuous spinal anaesthesia (CSA) provides extension of blockage during surgery and versatile pain management during the postoperative period via an

indwelling catheter allowed intermittent injection of local anaesthetic into the subarachnoid space. Better cardiovascular stability with a smaller dose of local anaesthetic and shorter surgery onset time were reported in CSA. [3]

Material and Method

The study was undertaken in the Department of Anaesthesiology, at Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Sciences, Pawapuri, Nalanda. Study duration May 2022 To April 2024. The study included 90 patients (age 20-35 years) undergoing elective caesarean section under spinal Anaesthesia. Pre-Anaesthetic check-up was done in all the patients which included:

1. Elucidating history of diabetes, hypertension, asthma, tuberculosis, previous cardiovascular or central nervous system abnormalities, drug allergy, previous surgery, or any other significant history.
2. Examination including pulse, blood pressure, cardiovascular examination, respiratory system examination, spinal abnormalities, other systems.
3. Investigations including haemoglobin,

complete blood counts, serum electrolytes, INR, blood sugar, serum urea, serum creatinine, chest X-ray, ECG asand when applicable.

Inclusion criteria

1. Woman of age between 20-35 years
2. ASA grade I or II
3. Undergoing elective caesarean section.

Exclusion criteria

1. Known hypertensive or those with a resting arterial pressure more than 130/90 mmHg.
2. Patient with hypovolemia or hypotension

3. Patients with diabetes, respiratory disease, cardiac disease, epilepsy.
4. Height less than 150 cm
5. Allergic to any drug to be used
6. Any other contraindication for spinal anaesthesia

Results

Baseline MAP and pulse observations

MAP (mean arterial pressure) = $(SBP+2DBP)/3=$
DBP+1/3PP

Mean of baseline MAP and Pulse in all the groups

Table 1:

	Group C	Group E	Group P
Baseline MAP	89.73±6.19	89.9±4.97	88.1±4.88
Baseline Pulse	92.8±10.06	94.13±11.83	92.1±12.88

Table 2: Comparison of various groups with respectto baseline MAP

	Group C & E	Group C & P	Group E & P
P value	0.9070	0.0848	0.1623
Significance	Not significant	Not significant	Not significant

Discussion

Ephedrine due to its predominantly β -agonist activity is expected to cause an increase in heart rate. On the other hand, phenylephrine, with predominant α -agonist action, causes a rise in the arterial blood pressure without any direct effect on the heart rate. This leads to activation of baroreceptor reflex and subsequent decrease in the heart rate indirectly. Bradycardia could also be caused by cardiac sympathetic denervation associated with high spinal block.

In our study only 2 patients in the phenylephrine group developed bradycardia for which IV glycopyrolate was given, rest of the patients werestable except transient tachycardia in few patients.

In the study by kohki nishikawa and associates (2002) [4], bradycardia (heart rate< 50bpm) after IM administration of phenylephrine was not observed in any of the groups. Also none of the patients in any group developed bradycardia in the study done by Ayorinde BT et al (2001) [5]. In both of these studies phenylephrine and ephedrine were administered IM prophylactically. Bradycardia was observed in various studies in patients receiving IV bolus or infusion ofphenylephrine either prophylactically ortherapeutically. (Dinesh Sahu et al 2003, Ngan Kee WD et al 2004) [6,7]

Conclusion

Vital parameters were monitored and blood pressure & heart rate reading were taken 3 times at 2 minutes interval and lowest MAP and heart rate were taken as baseline for each group respectively. All the

patients were preloaded with 500 ml of ringer lactate solution. Test drug was injected IM just after the induction of spinal anaesthesia. All the patients were observed and hemodynamic data recorded for 60 minutes after spinal anaesthesia.

The patients were monitored for hypotension(decrease in MAP>25% of baseline MAP), bradycardia (heart rate<50 beats/minute), nausea, vomiting.

References

1. Jackson R, Reid JA, Thorburn J. Volume preloading is not essential to prevent spinal induced hypotensionat caesarean section. Br J Anaesth 1995; 75:262-5.
2. Webb AA, Shipton EA. Re-evaluation of IM ephedrine as prophylaxis against hypotension associated with spinal anaesthesia for caesarean section Can J Anaesth 1998; 45:367-9.
3. Critchley LAH, Stuart JC, Conway F, Short TG. Hypotension during subarachnoid anaesthesia:hemodynamic effects of ephedrine. Br J Anaesth 1995; 74:373-8.
4. Kohki Nishikawa, MD, Michiaki Yamakage, MD PhD, Keiichi Omote, MD PhD, and Akiyoshi Namiki, MD PhD. Prophylactic IM small dose phenylephrine blunts spinal anaesthesia induced hypotensive response during surgical repair of hip fracture in the elderly. Anesth Analg 2002; 95:751-756.
5. Ayorinde B, Buczkowski P, Brown J et al. Evaluation ofpre-emptive intramuscular phenylephrine and ephedrine for reduction of spinal anaesthesia induced hypotension during

- caesarean section. Br J Anaesth 2001; 86:372-6.
6. Dr. Dinesh Sahu, Dr. Dilip Kothari, Dr. Amrita Mehrotra. Comparison of bolus phenylephrine, ephedrine, mephentermine for maintenance of arterial pressure during spinal anaesthesia in caesarean section – a clinical study. Indian J Anaesth 2003; 47 (2):125-128.
 7. Ngan Kee WD, Khaw KS, Ng FF, Lee BB. Prophylactic phenylephrine infusion for preventing hypotension during spinal anaesthesia for caesarean delivery. Anesth Analg 2004; 98:815-821.